

Effective use of modern methods in teaching foreign languages

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Annotation: This article highlights the importance of the effective use of modern pedagogical methods in the process of teaching foreign languages. The article critically analyzes traditional methods of teaching a foreign language, shows the advantages of using modern methodologies and innovative technologies. In particular, he explains how the use of a communicative approach, immersive technologies, audiovisual tools, interactive teaching methods, and virtual learning environments can help students learn a language quickly and effectively. Modern approaches to improving teachers' pedagogical qualifications in the process of teaching a foreign language, effective organization of lessons and practical assimilation of the language of students should be placed in the article. The application of technological innovations in the field of education and their impact on the language teaching process is analyzed in detail. Changes in innovative methods and teaching materials will allow students to develop thinking and communication skills, as well as to successfully function in cultural exchanges and global relations.

Keywords: Foreign language, modern methods, pedagogy, interactive approach, audiovisual technologies, immersive methods, teaching process, innovative technologies.

1 Introduction

Teaching foreign languages today is important not only for the development of students' language skills, but also for preparing them for success in a global communication environment. Global changes in the field of education and technological innovations have led to the emergence of new pedagogical approaches to teaching a foreign language. In parallel with this, traditional teaching methods are being fully adapted and updated in line with modern requirements. In particular, modern pedagogical methods – interactive and audiovisual methods, the use of new technologies, ensuring the active participation of students – play a role in teaching a foreign language effectively.

2 Methods and materials

This article discusses the possibility of using modern methods of teaching foreign languages and their advantages. The article gives specific recommendations to teachers on the choice of advanced methods of teaching a foreign language and their application in practice. Using modern approaches to teaching foreign languages will help to achieve more effective results by making the learning process more interactive and interesting for students. The article provides teachers with the necessary knowledge and skills to improve students' success in language learning through the use of methodological approaches and pedagogical innovations.

Teaching foreign languages today has become one of the most important issues not only for students, but also for society as a whole. The process of globalization, new technologies, intensifying intercultural dialogue and international cooperation make the importance of knowledge

of a foreign language deepening. Knowledge of a foreign language not only ensures professional success, but has become an integral part of personal development and cultural exchange. Thus, teaching a foreign language is regarded as one of the main directions of the education system. While traditional methods of teaching foreign languages retain their relevance, modern teaching methods and pedagogical approaches create new opportunities. Today, teachers pay great attention not only to the formation of solid knowledge, but also to the development of students' creative thinking, problem-solving and communication skills. It should be noted that new pedagogical methods and technologies play an important role in making the process of teaching a foreign language more interactive and effective. The use of modern methods will give students the opportunity to actively participate, express themselves and study the language in a hands-on way. All of these things help the student to quickly and efficiently learn the language. The article discusses how to effectively use modern methods in the process of learning a foreign language, including a communicative approach, immersive technologies, interactive lessons and audiovisual means. In particular, it will consider how new methods and technologies will create opportunities to engage students, develop their ability to think independently and apply language in a real context. At the same time, the article emphasizes the role of teachers in the selection of modern methods of teaching a foreign language, the importance of their professional development and familiarization with methodological approaches. The need to establish effective communication between teachers and students and introduce pedagogical innovations to make the educational process more effective is also mentioned.

3 Results and discussion

The process of teaching a foreign language requires constant change and innovation. Modern pedagogical approaches, technological innovations and the needs of students change every year, therefore, teachers must adapt to innovations when choosing effective methods of teaching a foreign language. Modern methods not only increase the effectiveness of language teaching, but also contribute to the development of students' creative thinking and communication skills. One of the most effective methods of teaching a foreign language is a communicative approach. This method is based on applying the language in the process of real-life communication, rather than learning a language only by grammar rules and vocabulary. Pupils need to be encouraged to use the language in a practical way, to guide them to learning the language through real life situations. This method helps the learners to learn the language lively, as a real communication medium. For example, teachers can organize work in groups, allowing students to perform a variety of communicative tasks. The use of modern technologies in the teaching of a foreign language will increase students' interest in the lessons. Interactive whiteboards, mobile apps, online platforms and language teaching programs provide students with new ways to learn. For example, interactive games, language exercises and audiovisual materials make students' learning a language more engaging and effective. At the same time, online learning opportunities help students learn the language on their own. Immersive (deep learning) methods are known as an effective approach to teaching a foreign language. In this method, students are encouraged to delve deeper into the language and master the language not only through practice, but also through the study of different cultures. Through immersive methods, it is possible to fully immerse students in the language, for example, to communicate with speakers of a foreign language, to apply the language in everyday life and to create opportunities to learn about different cultures. This method allows students to learn the language not only in grammatical terms, but also in cultural, social and psychological terms.

Audiovisual materials such as video, audio files, animations and films are effective tools for teaching a foreign language. Such materials allow students to learn the language in a more lively and natural context. Through videos and films, students learn the language completely by hearing and sight, while developing their listening and comprehension skills. Also, audiovisual tools motivate students and keep them interested in the lessons, which in turn makes the language learning process productive. Modern methods are aimed at ensuring the active participation of

students. In the classroom, great attention is paid to students' activity and independent thinking. For example, students learn a language through activities such as discussion, group work, or role-playing. These methods allow students not only to learn the language in theoretical terms, but also to apply it in practice. Modern pedagogy also considers the individual approach to be important. Each student learns the language in different ways according to their characteristics, level of knowledge, interests. Therefore, it is imperative that teachers organize lessons that are tailored to individual needs. For example, some learners prefer to work with more visual materials, while others prefer more listening and communication-based techniques. A teacher's choice of methods that are appropriate to each student's needs will help them learn effectively. In order for a foreign language teaching to be effective, teachers must constantly improve their skills. Knowledge of modern pedagogical methods, technologies and new approaches contributes to the professional development of teachers. Providing teachers with modern methodological manuals and information helps to improve their pedagogical skills. The use of modern methods in teaching foreign languages not only makes the learning of a foreign language effective, but also allows to motivate students, develop their communication skills and teach them how to apply the language in everyday life. Modern technologies and pedagogical approaches help to improve the teaching of foreign languages, consolidate students' knowledge and prepare them for global dialogue.

4 Conclusion

Effective use of modern methods in teaching foreign languages remains the most important requirement of today's education system. Due to globalization and the development of information technologies, learning foreign languages has become more interactive and dynamic. Modern pedagogical methods, including a communicative approach, immersive technologies, audiovisual materials and use of interactive tools, help improve the effectiveness of students' language learning. These methods not only make the learning language interesting and effective, but also give students the opportunity to apply the language in a real communicative context and understand its practical value. The success of learning a foreign language depends on motivating students, adapting them to their individual needs, as well as constantly improving the professional qualifications of teachers. Teachers develop not only their knowledge, but also their social and communicative skills by choosing innovative approaches to the use of modern technologies and methods in teaching their students. Also, increasing students' activity in mastering the language, accurately expressing their opinions and directing them to the effective use of the language in everyday life will help them to develop more solid knowledge. In addition, modern methods and innovative technologies allow for further individualization of the language teaching process, adapting it to the needs of each student and the pace of learning. Interactive approaches and immersive methods provide students with the opportunity to learn about culture, traditions, and worldviews, not just the language itself. This will help educate students who are ready and competent for global culture and international relations in the teaching of foreign languages. Thus, the effective use of modern methods in teaching foreign languages is an important tool not only to improve the level of knowledge of students, but also to provide them with new communication skills, to prepare them for successful work in the global world. The introduction of modern approaches in the educational process as well as the introduction of pedagogical innovations will significantly increase the effectiveness of foreign language teaching. Through the proper application of modern methods and technologies into their practice, teachers have a positive influence not only to teach the language, but also to the development of students.

References:

1. Abdullayeva, Markhabo. "The Appearance Of The Term “Education Dictionary” In World Linguistics Is Analyzed." *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences* 2.Special Issue 28-2 (2022): 48-52.

2. Aripova G. T. ADULTS TEACHING ENGLISH IN THE SPHERE OF ART AND CULTURE//Язык и культура.– 2018.– С. 72-81
3. Saidakbarova S. P. et al. The Role Of Speech Genres In The Communication Process //Educational Administration: Theory and Practice.– 2024.– Т. 30.– №. 5.– С. 2500-2503.
4. Dilafruz Bozorovna Botirova., Markhabo Raxmonkulovna Abdullayeva., Ilkhom Yusupovich Khaydarov., Ra’no Anvarovna Khaydarova., Shaxnoza Sharofovna Sharofova. Social Psychological Features of the Process of Professional Stress in Pedagogical Activity. Journal Power System Technology ISSN: 1000-3673. Publication date 2024/12. Volume 48, Issue 4. Pages 3325-3334. Publisher: <https://powertechjournal.com/index.php/journal>
5. Abdujabborova K. METHODOLOGY OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING TO JOURNALISM STUDENTS: EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES //Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research.– 2025.– Т. 12.– №. 02.– С. 42-46.
6. Galina Kan Arseniyevna. (2023). DEVELOPING LANGUAGE PROFICIENCY . Horizon: Journal of Humanity and Artificial Intelligence, 2(12), 52–55. Retrieved from <https://univerpubl.com/index.php/horizon/article/view/2971>
7. Abdujabarova K. K. K. THE ROLE OF AUDIO-VIDEO MATERIALS IN DEVELOPING INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences.– 2022.– Т. 2.– №. Special Issue 20.– С. 659-665.
8. Abdujabarova K. H. K. USE OF FICTION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS'SPEECH ACTIVITIES IN PRACTICAL CLASSES //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences.– 2021.– Т. 1.– №. 8.– С. 241-245.
9. ABDULLAYEVA MARXABO RAXMONKULOVNA. ENGLISH (FOR STUDENTS MAJORING IN ANTHROPOLOGY) O‘quv qo‘llanma. ISBN 978-9910-8696-1-7. 2025/1. Volume 1. Pages 286
10. Tulkunovna A. G. STUDY OF MUSIC TERMS IN COMPILING A DICTIONARY //Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS).– 2022.– Т. 1.– №. Conference DSMI.– С. 148-152.